

CoreTrustSeal: *Second Draft Consultation of the Recommendations on certifying the services required to enable FAIR research outputs within EOSC.* Feedback

The CoreTrustSeal¹ Board would like to thank the authors and members of the EOSC FAIR Working Group for the opportunity to respond to this *Second Draft Consultation*². In this public document, we provide our feedback with some selected extracts from the report to provide context. We welcome the well-considered and measured response to the issue of certification provided by the report, and appreciate the positive perspective on the work of CoreTrustSeal to date and the acknowledgment that trust is critical to the success of the EOSC and of global collaborative data infrastructures.

The report notes the active support and engagement with the FAIRsFAIR project work to date. We continue to monitor and cooperate with FAIRsFAIR, although any incorporation of proposed changes into the CoreTrustSeal Requirements or Processes will be subject to CoreTrustSeal Community consultation. We draw your attention to the draft model provided by FAIRsFAIR³ for the elaboration of requirements around the ‘core’ of CoreTrustSeal, which we see as a possible approach to interoperability with other standards and processes, as well as to integrations into the Requirements.

The report notes “*CoreTrustSeal is also working to extend their certification framework to additional groups of actors*”. This is correct, though our initial focus is on the appropriate support for, and differentiation between, generalist and specialist (e.g., disciplinary and domain) repositories along with services for assuring the long-term preservation of digital objects.

Though primarily data-service oriented, the CoreTrustSeal sees the benefits of increasing alignment and compatibility with other standards, whether for FAIR enabling repositories, open data initiatives, or the development of minimum expectations for IT service management.

We would sound a note of caution around the use of the term “*self-certify*” in the report and would prefer to see terms reflecting a continuum of increasingly trusted assessments: self-assessment, peer review, audit etc. . We would suggest that certification standards, processes, and bodies should be clearly defined and subject to transparent standards themselves. As noted in the report, it is desirable that “*organisations overseeing certification schemes are independent, trusted, sustainable and scalable*”. We would extend this expectation to the development, maintenance, and implementation of the wide range of standards, semantic artefacts, registries, and other services that we all rely on.

There are a range of standards and supporting measures to ensure assessment, evaluation, and compliance that might be applied to different aspects of research data infrastructures.

¹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4284666>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4003598>

We are particularly interested in the development of shared standardised metadata around repository data services and the objects they curate. If suitably validated, this metadata might provide for (semi-)automated validation of repository and object statuses that could streamline certification and provide the foundation for more rich contextual semantic data. As covered in the report, this is an important potential route to scalability.

We can certainly support the key recommendations, assuming that appropriate prioritisation, resourcing, and consideration of interdependencies are in place:

Priority 1: Support the current efforts to align Certification schemas with FAIR

Priority 2: Test the proposed schema in a variety of communities to gather feedback and update the proposed framework accordingly.

Priority 3: Provide support, methodologically as well as financially, to data and service providers to progress towards certification.

Priority 4: Monitor the progress of certification, assess the maturity of the certification landscape, and take appropriate action if fields or regions are lagging behind.

Priority 5: Support the establishment of criteria and methodology to certify other key elements of the FAIR ecosystem, in particular PID services and vocabulary repositories/ metadata registries, and test them extensively.

Priority 6: Support the establishment and maintenance of registries of certified components of the ecosystem; if several registries are available for a given component, they should be harvestable and included in a registry of registries.

Priority 7: Establish a Working Group under the EOSC Stakeholder Forum to ensure the implementation and further development of recommendations in this report.”

We support, and see CoreTrustSeal as part of, the “*web of FAIR data and services*” envisioned. Many aspects of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements⁴ necessarily cover organisational, object, and technical measures applicable to a wide range of repositories, and data and metadata services, that do not include preservation in their remit.

CoreTrustSeal community members are active in the provision of data infrastructure and are very familiar with “*the uneven level of preparedness of the services and communities*”. This is one reason we seek to define core expectations while welcoming a wide range of candidates. We see trustworthiness as a journey in much the same way as the EOSC sees FAIR as a journey. We appreciate the “*community concerns with metrics and certification*”, but the prioritisation of development in areas such as metadata and ontologies should be seen as perfectly aligned with the eventual goal of certification. Assessment, including through certification and metrics, should certainly not be seen as punitive or be the subject of negative comparisons. Instead it provides a level of consistency and transparency that supports the clarification of ideal practice and interoperable cooperation among peers.

The report is correct to note that “*certifying a repository involves costs*”, but it also provides (acknowledged) benefits. CoreTrustSeal seeks to require a ‘core’ level of evidence that is intended to demonstrate that digital objects can be preserved within a sustainable

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3638211>

organisation. Maintenance of that evidence at a level sufficient to deliver the expected quality of service should also be sufficient to maintain certification. Services that do not meet these quality levels present a risk of adverse consequences.

Given the EOSC focus on FAIR data within FAIR-enabling data services, we hope that the future Working Group of the EOSC Stakeholder Forum monitoring this area of development sees certification and metrics as complementary. We support the following statements from the report:

“At this stage, because of the need for inclusiveness and the different stages of preparedness of the communities and their services, certification status cannot be a necessary condition for a repository to be included in EOSC.

At some point, certification might become a prerequisite for inclusion in EOSC, in particular for data repositories. This could be decided only after a careful assessment of the certification landscape and of the possible adverse consequences.

We strongly recommend that repositories and services wanting to join EOSC use the certification framework criteria to check and improve their practices, with the aim to progress towards certification.”

We appreciate the statement that CoreTrustSeal “*is a community-driven, international framework used by a large palette of disciplines*” that is the “*right level for research data repositories managed in the research environment*”. We see the work to develop certification and metrics around the EOSC as an important contribution to the emerging global efforts that help define, improve, and reap benefits from our connected network of global data infrastructures. The CoreTrustSeal Board and community look forward to cooperating on repository and data service standards and assessment processes in the future.

We would like to particularly highlight the report’s important coverage of the wide national and global variations in data and data service maturity. A focus on the need to provide extensive support and guidance is necessary. The value of certification does not eclipse the value of the data we hold on behalf of others.